

ReSChape

INNOVATIVE WAYS TO TRANSFORM SUPPLY CHAIN PROCESSES: MULTIPLE CASE STUDY IN EUROPE

This industrial briefly, as part of the ReSChape project, aims at providing some recommendations for practitioners regarding how European companies should address sustainability risks and build resilience along their supply chain (SC) processes. 18 case studies have been conducted among four European countries; the cases provide a comprehensive view of how companies are transforming their processes along the SC.

OCTOBER 2024

PROJECT PARTNERS

Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche

RESCHAPE PROJECT
IS FUNDED BY THE
EUROPEAN UNION

Introduction

Recent years have seen significant global changes impacting economies and societies, with lasting effects. Key factors include globalization, technological advancement, and shifting consumer demands, leading to increased supply chain volatility and uncertainty. Major crises such as COVID-19, the war in Ukraine, and Brexit, alongside issues like overpopulation and water scarcity, have further disrupted supply chains. To address these challenges, future supply chains must be resilient, sustainable, and socially responsible. This requires collaboration among governments, businesses, civil society, and consumers, using innovative practices and technologies to improve resilience and sustainability.

The ReSChape project was funded by the European Commission and started in October 2022.

During the 3 years of the project, the consortium aims to analyse social, economic and environmental changes and disruptions, and evaluate their impact on supply chains. Moreover, the project studies innovative supply chain models, aiming towards streamlined processes to assure humans (workers, consumers and citizens) are at the centre of the business thanks to new digital technologies. The results will be complemented with the definition of policy scenarios and recommendations to support sustainability and resilience in supply chains.

Case study analysis

The sample of companies was chosen to be heterogeneous in terms of business, i.e. type of organization and sector. Case studies have been selected among European companies placed in Italy, Germany, Portugal and Spain and with an implemented sustainability strategy which involves also their supply chain (like benefit companies, Bcorp, sustainability certifications, CSR report). Large companies and SMEs (including innovative start-ups) participated in the study to gather multiple perspectives.

Fig.1. Dimensions of the analysis.

The collection of case studies was based on interviews with managers to investigate the most important sustainability risks, such as environmental, social and technological risks for the supply chain and the actions by which companies are transforming their supply chain processes (Fig. 1). Data have been collected between October 2023 and February 2024.

Capabilities to transform Supply Chains

The actions have been analysed investigating which capabilities have been leveraged to transform

Collaboration

Collaboration is one of the formative elements of resilience as well as a driver of sustainability thanks to the involvement of many different actors at the internal or external level, such as suppliers, competitors, technological providers, policymakers, and consumers. The joint collaborative processes enable companies to develop innovative and transformative actions along their supply chains, such as Eco-design and sustainable purchasing.

Technological innovation

Technological innovation enables companies to face disruptions and manage risks. The orientation of companies towards innovation and digital technologies supports resilience development and transformative paths are enabled by the innovative use of technologies to engage suppliers, customers and even society, such as new ways to recover scraps, tracking systems to ensure transparency of prices and blockchain technology to monitor suppliers.

Learning

Learning is related to training, learning from experience and knowledge management. Concerning the transformative approach to resilience it means creating and sharing knowledge within the firm, transferring and sharing knowledge across the sector and the broader supply chain, and exchanging and sharing knowledge with the wider ecosystem.

The SC processes considered in the analysis of the capabilities are: design, sourcing, manufacturing, delivery and return.

Recommendations for practitioners

European companies are increasingly adopting a transformative approach to embrace social and environmental sustainability, involving not only supply chain actors but also different kind of stakeholders with a broader perspective. This evolution encompasses the entire lifecycle of products, from conception through disposal and recycling, directly engaging consumers and society. The success of businesses is now measured beyond traditional metrics like revenues, including factors such as working conditions, consumer satisfaction, community engagement, and environmental protection.

Social sustainability

For what concerns social sustainability, companies need to develop actions such as training and wealth initiatives both for local and global suppliers (including suppliers in developing countries), investment in local community culture, preserving craftsmanship skills, and training programmes for energy saving. These actions require a human-centric transformation within companies and along their supply chains. This transformation should be based on a multidimensional approach that places human needs, knowledge and experiences at the centre of design, development and implementation of the new supply chains where technological solutions and new learning practices not only meet workers' functional requirements (i.e. safety) but also enhance human well-being, capabilities and working conditions. Some recommendations for practitioners can be summarised as follow:

- **Optimise the interactions between individuals and machines**, strengthen human centricity when designing processes, systems and work environments to enhance employee engagement, well-being and productivity.
- **Assure that technology adoption along all the supply chain** preserve individual's autonomy and privacy and respect human values.
- Actively **encourage skill development and continuous learning** among employees (white and blue collars) to ensure adaptability to technology development. Companies need to foster a culture of collaboration and inclusivity, especially in global supply chains, involving also 2nd and 3rd-tier suppliers as well as local communities, higher education institutions and local associations.
- Assure cross-company **training opportunities, stimulating motivation and awareness on sustainability issues** also through supportive and trust-based management such as direct participation and workforce empowerment, and with induction programmes.
- Apply **supplier development strategies** where direct control is merged with a collaborative approach to support the application of the code of conduct to respect regulations and assure corporate social responsibility. Technologies like blockchain and digital platforms can help not only share production data but also information related to workers' conditions at supplier premises.

Environmental sustainability

For what concerns environmental sustainability, companies need to develop actions such as eco-design, waste recycling, decarbonisation of processes, and adoption of certified green products. These actions require a transformation within companies and along their supply chains in terms of circularity and R-strategies developed where processes like design, sourcing and others need to be appropriately re-engineered. Some recommendations for practitioners are related to:

- Apply a **sustainable “by design” approach**, embracing risk management and sustainability issues during the design of processes and products. The effectiveness of implementing sustainable actions is more than ever linked to their impact all along the life cycle and applying proactive approaches with the support of the ecosystem.
- Invest in **circular economy models based on R-strategies** with actions like Recycling, Re-manufacturing, and Reuse as a way to implement an innovative approach to integrate competences, capacities and technologies. In particular, it is important to implement cross-sectorial models where the by-products of a sector can have innovative applications in others, or new collaborative approaches with customers to recover end-of-life products and treat them with appropriate technologies.
- **Towards Zero emission processes:** use of alternative energy sources such as hydrogen and renewable ones. Develop solutions to control and reduce emissions of polluting substances such GHG in industrial processes.

Overall, shedding light on the main insights derived from the case studies, other recommendations are related to:

- Increase **involvement of citizens and communities** in supply chain processes to face social challenges. Social innovation needs to merge with business to ensure companies go beyond traditional economic values.
- Develop in managers a **sustainability oriented mindset** to assure the proactiveness of the company and the supply chain towards green and social innovation.
- Enhance **the dialogue between the private and public sectors** to communicate the sustainability value of business actions. Industry and public bodies can thus jointly build ecosystems to support the competitiveness of a sector or a country and increase the well-being of the society.

The future competitiveness of European supply chains hinges on embracing an ecosystem approach. To achieve resilience and environmental, social and economic sustainability, companies need to overcome the traditional supply chain boundaries towards the entire ecosystem. Thus, companies should involve second, third and n-tier suppliers, competitors, policymakers, and local communities to achieve the desired targets for resilience and sustainability. Through collaboration activities and the development and transfer of knowledge, they can also develop a higher level of technological innovation.

Summary of the case study

Actions for sustainability and resilience	Actions for sustainability and resilience
Case A: BCorp certified startup in developing countries	Case J: Industrial symbiosis for sustainability in the steel sector
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A1: Selection of sustainable suppliers in Africa • A2: Training and wealth initiatives for workers in developing countries • A3: Investment in local communities' culture • A4: Transparency of price 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • J1: Heat recovery • J2: Waste recycling
Case B: Social and environmental sustainability in luxury	Case K: Green transition in the steel sector for decarbonisation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • B1: Preventive measures for sustainability compliance • B2: Attracting and developing talents • B3: Alliances to push the ecosystem's compliance to environmental standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • K1: Decarbonisation of processes • K2: Real-Time Eco-Impact Tracking • K3: Fostering Corporate awareness through social media
Case C: Craftmanship and local communities for Made in Italy	Case L: Proactive strategies for green and certified steel
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • C1: Preserving craftsmanship skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • L1: Optimisation of transportation efficiency • L2: Green energy • L3: Certified green steel
Case D: Networking SMEs for sustainability	Case M: Social and environmentally sustainable transportation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D1: Monitoring outsourced processes for value chain sustainability compliance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • M1: Real-time control of supply chain • M2: Training programmes for energy savings • M3: Monitoring alternative energy sources for clean transport
Case E: New ecosystems for sustainable footwear	Case N: Urban logistics electrification to decarbonize and comply with new regulations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E1: Eco-design • E2: Creation of a capillary and certified network of repairing services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N1: Urban logistics electrification to decarbonize and comply with new regulations
Case F: Global and transparent value chain for sustainable footwear	Case O: Zero Emissions Urban Freight Logistics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • F1: Traceability for monitoring suppliers' sustainability compliance • F2: Creation of virtual prototypes • F3: Eco-design and use of recycled materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • O1: Zero emissions urban freight logistics
Case G: Circular textile supply chain	Case P: Digital mobility service for at-home healthy food delivery socially inclusive
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • G1: Decentralization of suppliers of raw materials • G2: Recycling and reusing fabric scraps • G3: Restructuring of production processes: Achieve energy savings through the introduction of green equipment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P1: Digital mobility service for at-home healthy food delivery socially inclusive
Case H: Digital technologies for textile optimisation	Case Q: Human-centred retail supply chain
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • H1: Waste management in textile production • H2: Artificial Intelligence for resource efficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Q1: Business model "with you" • Q2: Comprehensive Ethical Initiative • Q3: Net zero commitment • Q4: Zero Food Waste
Case I: Design4sustainability in sportswear	Case R: Sustainable digital printing for packaging
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I1: Eco-design using recycled materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R1: Navigating the Future of Recycling and Reusability • R2: Revamping Supply Chains: Shifting from Asia to Europe for Enhanced Integration and Sustainability

Results of the case studies

This brief describes the main evidence emerged from 18 case studies including large enterprises and SMEs in Germany, Italy, Portugal and Spain. These companies belong to different ecosystems such as textile (e.g. sportswear, clothing and footwear), energy-intensive (e.g. steel and metal), retail (i.e. large distributors) and mobility and transport.

More than 40 actions for sustainability have been collected from the companies. These actions have been coded according to the 3 capabilities of the model (collaboration, technological innovation and learning).

Design process

In the design process, companies implement actions like Eco-design by involving suppliers and external actors to develop sustainable solutions by overcoming the supply chain borders.

In the textile ecosystem, companies are asked to adopt certified, recyclable and recycled materials and to develop innovative materials by fostering strong partnerships with suppliers through the definition of long-term agreements (I1). Moreover, developing Eco-design includes the adoption of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) to measure the carbon footprint allowing the design of new products with reduced impact on sustainability (E1). Virtual Reality have been adopted to support digital product development (F3), thus eliminating waste due to physical prototypes and reducing operating times in the interaction with customers. Sharing prototype models through cloud platforms transforms the way companies collaborate with their customers and suppliers during the design phase.

Sourcing process

Aiming at responsible and transparent procurement, companies adopt selection, traceability and monitoring practices to assure suppliers' sustainability compliance both in social and environmental terms.

Thanks to blockchain technologies, companies can collect certificates of sustainability and quality compliance of suppliers thus guaranteeing transparency and product anti-counterfeiting. These actions have been extended to second and third-tier suppliers to ensure that ecosystem actors also comply with sustainability standards (D1). Moreover, to prevent social risks such as violation of human rights, companies are asked to carry out on-site audits and inspections of suppliers' production sites located in developing countries (B3).

Similarly, as investigated in the energy-intensive ecosystem (L3), companies implement tracking systems, such as those cloud-based, to provide transparency and traceability of their product, to monitor and verify the sustainability credentials of their supply chain and adhere to environmental (K2) and ethical standards.

In retail sector, sourcing processes are transformed by involving suppliers through collaborative approaches to integrate environmental and social policies to improve the offer (Q3).

Manufacturing process

Companies adopt a human-centric approach to managing workers' needs along the supply chain with wealth-oriented initiatives.

Training programmes for workers, as in the textile sector (A2), leverage on learning process and aim at increasing social sustainability through skills enhancement and improved wellbeing at the workplace. For instance, enhancing craftsmanship skills is particularly relevant in ecosystems based on the tradition and originality of products such as the textile one (C1). Investments in local communities both with tangible and intangible assets, enable the development of trust and collaboration throughout the local value chain, increasing social sustainability.

Decarbonisation of processes aiming for CO₂ neutrality is particularly relevant for the transformation of the energy-intensive ecosystem (K1, K2) and relies on leveraging new technologies to transition the annealing process from gas to hydrogen or electricity. The implementation of real-time CO₂ footprint tracking for products (such as in K2) directly impacts sustainability by fostering transparency and environmental accountability thus attracting conscious customers of the steel sector.

Delivery process

Companies are particularly committed to the transition to alternative energies and optimization of transport for the enhancement of environmental and social sustainability.

Companies are asked to adopt track and trace tools for real-time monitoring of clients' and suppliers' information and delivery optimization technologies (such as in M1). Moreover, as analysed in the textile sector (A4), companies provide transparency in terms of cost of sustainability and promote social benefits by leveraging technologies such as B2C platforms, social media and tracking systems. Finally, local trade is promoted in the retail sector (Q1), where companies foster closer relationships with client partners thanks to local suppliers.

Return process

Return process are gaining importance due to the increasing need to manage waste, by-product, reverse logistics.

Steel industry is investing in innovative technology for heat recovery in collaboration with municipalities and utilities (J1) as well as in waste recycling actions for industrial symbiosis to reuse metal scraps (J2).

Recycling and reusing scraps characterize also other ecosystems such as the textile (G2, E2). Zero food waste initiatives in retail (Q4) contribute also to the welfare of community with the active involvement of customers for donation to food banks. Other transformative actions promote product life extension enlarging ecosystem through the involvement of other actors such as repairing services in textile (E2).

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Annex

Case A: BCorp certified startup in developing countries

The Company, established in 2018, is an Italian ethical fashion brand specializing in collections crafted from African fabrics with Italian design. The SME operates with a female workforce across all processes, achieving a gender pay gap of 0. Design is in Italy while production occurs in Africa, training local tailors. Fabrics are also sourced locally, supporting micro-economies, and fostering community partnerships.

Actions for sustainability and resilience

- A1: Selection of sustainable suppliers in Africa
 - A2: Training and wealth initiatives for workers in developing countries
 - A3: Investment in local communities' culture
 - A4: Transparency of price
-

Case B: Social and environmental sustainability in luxury

The company is a very large enterprise in the fashion sector renowned for the design, production, and sales of luxury goods for men and women, including footwear, leather goods, clothing, jewellery, and accessories. Its products are distinguished by exclusivity, combining creative style, innovation, and Italian craftsmanship. The supply chain relies on highly skilled suppliers, primarily Italian ones.

Actions for sustainability and resilience

- B1: Preventive measures for sustainability compliance
 - B2: Attracting and developing talents
 - B3: Alliances to push the ecosystem's compliance to environmental standards
-

Case C: Craftmanship and local communities for Made in Italy

This large company is renowned for luxury brand cashmere sweaters that produces and sells clothing and accessories for men, women, and children. The company's mission is to "create beauty", preserve culture and give value to tradition. All its products are handmade with the highest quality materials, relying on the manual skills and craftsmanship of local suppliers. It focuses on micro-enterprises enabling a generational shift among the artisans.

Actions for sustainability and resilience

- C1: Preserving craftsmanship skills
-

Case D: Networking SMEs for sustainability

This holding is composed of 11 SMEs specialized in fashion items for luxury brands and is part of a larger textile ecosystem holding. These SMEs produce various products, including jersey, leather, and denim clothing, sportswear, bags, small leather goods, and shoes, and offer digital printing on fabrics and embroidery services. The Group employs almost 800 people, with more than half being women. It works with more than 400 local suppliers.

Actions for sustainability and resilience

- D1: Monitoring outsourced processes for value chain sustainability compliance

Case E: New ecosystems for sustainable footwear

This large company is a leader in the high-performance soles industry, that develops and manufactures rubber soles for outdoor and leisure activities, workwear, fashion, orthopaedics, and repair, along with a line of finished shoes. Suppliers are located close to production sites to support a zero-mile production approach. Production is both internal and outsourced to third-party manufacturers.

Actions for sustainability and resilience

- E1: Eco-design
 - E2: Creation of a capillary and certified network of repairing services
-

Case F: Global and transparent value chain for sustainable footwear

The SME operates in the footwear industry, by creating, developing and acquiring brands, licenses and patents. The main activities are dedicated to the design and creation of footwear through its brands, emphasizing "Made in Italy" craftsmanship. Sustainability is embedded in the company's ethos, influencing supplier selection, product innovation, raw material choices, product safety, employee welfare, and community engagement.

Actions for sustainability and resilience

- F1: Traceability for monitoring suppliers' sustainability compliance
 - F2: Creation of virtual prototypes
 - F3: Eco-design and use of recycled materials
-

Case G: Circular textile supply chain

This Portuguese SME is specialized in products for hotels, decoration, and home solutions. Thanks to the quality of its products and a focus on innovation and service, it holds a strong position in the global market for textile production in the field. Its approach is also characterized by continuous investment in the training of human resources and in industrial equipment of advanced technology.

Actions for sustainability and resilience

- G1: Decentralization of suppliers of raw materials
 - G2: Recycling and reusing fabric scraps
 - G3: Restructuring of production processes: Achieve energy savings through the introduction of green equipment
-

Case H: Digital technologies for textile optimisation

This SME is specialized in developing software based on artificial intelligence solutions tailored for the textile industry. By integrating different technologies, the company facilitates manufacturing defect detection, prevention, and prediction, as well as implements energy reduction systems and waste management capabilities. This allows them to respond directly to fashion brands' demands for enhanced supply chain transparency and collaboration.

Actions for sustainability and resilience

- H1: Waste management in textile production
- H2: Artificial Intelligence for resource efficiency

Case I: Design4sustainability in sportswear

This Spanish company is an SME that manages multiple brands exclusively dedicated to outdoor apparel, well known for its commitment to sustainable practices. Specializing in designing and producing environmentally friendly outdoor clothing and gear, it emphasizes innovation and cutting-edge technologies to create high-performance sportswear.

Actions for sustainability and resilience

- I1: Eco-design using recycled materials
-

Case J: Industrial symbiosis for sustainability in the steel sector

This large company is a leader in producing high quality steels for automotive, mechanical, energy, and construction sectors. It operates through a group consolidated from ten companies across various segments of the steel industry, ensuring full traceability and high-quality end products. The headquartered is in Northern Italy, and its operations encompass steel furnaces, rolling mills, and heat treatment processes.

Actions for sustainability and resilience

- J1: Heat recovery
 - J2: Waste recycling
-

Case K: Green transition in the steel sector for decarbonisation

Based in Germany's industrial heartland, this large company excels in the energy-intensive sector, specializing in the production of cold-rolled steel strips. It offers a diverse product portfolio tailored to various industrial applications. Its products are thus distinguished by high quality and cost-effectiveness, meeting stringent material standards across multiple sectors such as automotive, construction, machinery manufacturing, and precision engineering.

Actions for sustainability and resilience

- K1: Decarbonisation of processes
 - K2: Real-Time Eco-Impact Tracking
 - K3: Fostering Corporate awareness through social media
-

Case L: Proactive strategies for green and certified steel

This large company is a leading German retailer specialising in distributing steel products across diverse industries, including construction, automotive, and machinery manufacturing. Operating primarily in Europe, it prioritizes innovation to ensure efficient as well as ethical-based supply chains. The Company reinforces its commitment to responsible practices focusing on strategic energy management and investments in renewable energy sources.

Actions for sustainability and resilience

- L1: Optimisation of transportation efficiency
- L2: Green energy
- L3: Certified green steel

Case M: Social and environmentally sustainable transportation

Founded 70 years ago, the company is a large Portuguese logistics and transportation organization. It specializes in providing integrated logistics services across the Iberian Peninsula, with more than 20 logistics centres. These centres are strategically located across different regions to optimize logistical operations and meet the diverse needs of its customers.

Actions for sustainability and resilience

- M1: Real-time control of supply chain
 - M2: Training programmes for energy savings
 - M3: Monitoring alternative energy sources for clean transport
-

Case N: Urban logistics electrification to decarbonize and comply with new regulations

To protect society from the impacts of road traffic (pollution, noise, congestion, etc.), some city areas are restricting the use of internal combustion engine (ICE) vehicles and allowing only vehicles with no emissions, to circulate (in low emission zones). Transport companies and specifically last mile delivery operators in the logistics sectors (transport, storage, delivery) need to adapt to new circumstances and city requirements to operate.

Actions for sustainability and resilience

- N1: Urban logistics electrification to decarbonize and comply with new regulations
-

Case O: Zero Emissions Urban Freight Logistics

City logistics plays a pivotal role in achieving lower emissions. Key measures include promoting higher vehicle load factors and establishing collection centres to facilitate zero-emission distributions. Companies in this sector aim to deliver large items originating from commercial furniture stores to final customers. These items are consolidated and shipped to a micro-hub using electric vehicles. Thus, logistics operations are optimized for the new configuration with internal combustion engine (ICE) vehicles.

Actions for sustainability and resilience

- O1: Zero emissions urban freight logistics
-

Case P: Digital mobility service for at-home healthy food delivery socially inclusive

Logistics service providers need to develop on-demand cycle-logistics food delivery services more accessible to low-income households, and non-digitally connected and socially isolated people. Digital services related to at-home food delivery rely on an app installed on a mobile phone, tablet or computer and provides prepared food from a variety of local restaurants or products from local stores delivered at home.

Actions for sustainability and resilience

- P1: Digital mobility service for at-home healthy food delivery socially inclusive

Case Q: Human-centred retail supply chain

This large company operates a vast network of supermarkets, hypermarkets, and convenience stores with a turnover of more than 5400 million euros in 2022. It stands out for its cooperative business model where employees are also owners, fostering inclusivity and participation in decision-making among its 9,500 workforce. Focused exclusively on the Spanish market, the company partners with over 9,000 suppliers, primarily local, to provide a wide array of products ranging from fresh produce to electronics and clothing, emphasizing quality and sustainability.

Actions for sustainability and resilience

- Q1: Business model “with you”
 - Q2: Comprehensive Ethical Initiative
 - Q3: Net zero commitment
 - Q4: Zero Food Waste
-

Case R: Sustainable digital printing for packaging

This large German company is a leader in digital printing solutions. It has significantly innovated the industry with its Single-Pass Digital Printing Systems tailored for corrugated and folding cartons. These systems integrate advanced inkjet technology to achieve high productivity and exceptional print quality. Through localized supply chains and renewable energy adoption, the company sets industry standards in sustainability practices.

Actions for sustainability and resilience

- R1: Navigating the Future of Recycling and Reusability
- R2: Revamping Supply Chains: Shifting from Asia to Europe for Enhanced Integration and Sustainability

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. **101061729**.

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